

***Importing multiple spreadsheets in an Excel
Workbook: An introduction to Macros
Paper SA-09-2015***

Nathan Becker - Statistical Analyst
William Muntean - Psychometrician
Pearson VUE

Overview

- Every week our team processes client data.
- Need to verify content of the data.
- Quarterly the data in the Excel files changes.
- Format of the data never changes just information in Excel files.

Introduction

- Simplify importing Excel files
- Minimize code changes
- One step solution for importing data
- Reusable code

Excel File Input

	A	B	C
1	Client_Name	Date	Cost
2	HP	9/15/2015	83.29
3	Apple	10/5/2015	111.45
4	IBM	11/26/2015	92.79
5	Tesla	9/26/2015	182.78

Client_1	Client_2	Client_3	Client_4
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Create Library Name

- Create Macro variable of file location and name.

```
%Let File = 'C:\ExcelFile.xlsx';  
LIBNAME XDATA &File;
```


Get Excel Sheet Names

- Use Proc Contents to retrieve data.

- ▣ **PROC CONTENTS**

```
DATA=XDATA. _ALL_ NOPRINT  
OUT=Sheets (KEEP=Memname) ;
```


Proc Contents as Data set

- Subset of Proc Contents

	▲ LIBNAME	▲ MEMNAME	▲ NAME	⑫	TYPE	⑫	LENGTH	▲ FORMAT
1	XDATA	Client_1\$	Client_Name		2		5	\$
2	XDATA	Client_1\$	Cost		1		8	
3	XDATA	Client_1\$	Date		1		8	DATE
4	XDATA	Client_2\$	Client_Name		2		6	\$
5	XDATA	Client_2\$	Cost		1		8	
6	XDATA	Client_2\$	Date		1		8	DATE
7	XDATA	Client_3\$	Client_Name		2		10	\$
8	XDATA	Client_3\$	Cost		2		5	\$
9	XDATA	Client_3\$	Date		1		8	DATE
10	XDATA	Client_4\$	Client_Name		2		9	\$
11	XDATA	Client_4\$	Cost		2		5	\$
12	XDATA	Client_4\$	Date		1		8	DATE

Cleaning up the data set

- Remove duplicates and sort data.

```
PROC SORT DATA=Sheets  
NODUPLICATES;  
BY Memname;
```


Cleaning (Cont.)

- Add ID to dataset and remove \$ associated with sheet names.

```
DATA Sheets;  
SET Sheets;  
ID=_N_;  
Memname =  
SUBSTR (Memname, 1,  
Length (Memname) -1);
```


Data Set 'Sheets'

- Final data set after Proc Contents, removing duplicates, sorting and adding ID column.

		ID
1	Client_1	1
2	Client_2	2
3	Client_3	3
4	Client_4	4

Get number of sheets in the Excel file

- Use SYMPUT to create Macro variable of the sheet count.

```
DATA _NULL_ ;  
    IF 0 THEN SET Sheets NOBS=X;  
    CALL SYMPUT ('Recount', X);  
    STOP;
```


Importing the Excel sheets into SAS

- Use a Do loop to import data into SAS datasets.

```
%DO i = 1 %TO &Recount;
```

```
▫ PROC SQL NOPRINT;
```

```
    SELECT Memname INTO :Name  
    FROM Sheets WHERE ID = &i;
```

```
▫ PROC SQL;
```

```
    CONNECT TO EXCEL (PATH=&File);  
    CREATE TABLE &Name AS  
    SELECT * FROM CONNECTION TO EXCEL  
    (SELECT * FROM [&Name.$]);  
    DISCONNECT FROM EXCEL;  
    QUIT;
```

```
%END;
```


Output in SAS

- Excel sheet from before now in SAS as a data set.

	A	B	C
1	Client_Name	Date	Cost
2	HP	9/15/2015	83.29
3	Apple	10/5/2015	111.45
4	IBM	11/26/2015	92.79
5	Tesla	9/26/2015	182.78

	Client_Name	Date	Cost
1	HP	15SEP2015	83.29
2	Apple	05OCT2015	111.45
3	IBM	26NOV2015	92.79
4	Tesla	26SEP2015	182.78

Creating a macro

- Change

```
%Let File = 'C:\ExcelFile.xlsx';
```

- To

```
%macro Excel(File = "NA");
```


Creating a macro (Cont.)

- Add the following to the end of the Program.

```
%mend;
```

```
%Excel(File = 'C:\ExcelFile.xlsx');
```


Limitations

- Column names required.
- Need to know file name.
- Sheet names should be one word.
- Connect to Excel is not supported in SAS Base, use Proc Import.
- Proc SQL allows Excel file to be open, Proc Import does not.

Contact Information

Name: Nathan Becker

E-mail: nathan.becker@pearson.com

